

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XLVII. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with OON Tridentate and OON-NOO Bis-tridentate Chelating Azodye Ligands 4-Methyl-1-(2'-hydroxy 3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonicphenylazo-1')benzene and 1,3-Bis-(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonicphenylazo-1')benzene

BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA,* APARNA, S. P. MISHRA and SAMBHU P. PRADHAN

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, G. M. Autonomous College, Sambalpur-768 004

Manuscript received 10 June 1993, revised 1 March 1994, accepted 22 March 1994

In continuation of our work¹ on the synthesis of polynuclear transition and non-transition metal complexes containing multidentate chelating azodye ligands, we describe here preparation and characterisation of one OON donor tridentate and one OON-NOO donor bis-tridentate azodyes and their dinuclear and tetranuclear metal complexes with bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg.

Results and Discussion

The dinuclear complexes have the compositions $[M_2L_2(H_2O)_4].[M_2'L_2]$ and the tetranuclear complexes $[M_4L_2(H_2O)_8].[M_4L'_2]$, where M(ii) = Co, Ni, Cu, M'(ii) = Zn, Cd and Hg; LH_2 = 4-methyl-1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonicphenylazo-1')benzene, $L'H_4$ = 1,3-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonicphenylazo-1')benzene. All the complexes (Table 1) are amorphous having high melting points, and insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in dimethyl formamide. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is shown from low conductance values ($2.2-4.6 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

In the ir spectra of ligands, the bands at 2 850, 2 920 cm^{-1} (LH_2) and 2 840-2 980 cm^{-1} ($L'H_4$) assignable to OH may be due to the presence of O-H...O and O-H...N intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The absence of these bands in the metal chelates

indicates the bonding of phenolic OH groups to the metal ions. The sharp bands at 1 470 cm^{-1}

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			
	M	C	H	N
LH_2 (Reddish brown)		49.5 (50.0)	3.3 (3.57)	8.1 (8.33)
$[Co_2L_2(H_2O)_4]$ (Dark brown)	13.4 (13.7)	38.8 (39.1)	3.1 (3.2)	6.2 (6.5)
$[Ni_2L_2(H_2O)_4]$ (Grey)	13.4 (13.6)	38.8 (39.2)	3.1 (3.2)	6.4 (6.5)
$[Cu_2L_2(H_2O)_4]$ (Black)	14.4 (14.6)	38.8 (38.7)	3.1 (3.2)	6.4 (6.4)
$[Zn_2L_2]$ (Reddish grey)	16.2 (16.4)	41.08 (42.0)	2.3 (2.5)	6.8 (7.0)
$[Cd_2L_2]$ (Grey)	24.9 (25.2)	37.4 (37.6)	2.1 (2.2)	6.1 (6.3)
$L'H_4$ (Black)		41.8 (42.4)	3.4 (3.5)	9.6 (9.9)
$[Co_4L'_2(H_2O)_8]$ (Reddish brown)	15.2 (15.6)	31.6 (31.9)	2.15 (2.4)	7.3 (9.9)
$[Ni_4L'_2(H_2O)_8]$ (Black)	15.4 (15.6)	31.6 (31.9)	2.27 (2.4)	7.4 (7.4)
$[Cu_4L'_2(H_2O)_8]$ (Dark brown)	16.5 (16.7)	31.4 (31.5)	2.29 (2.3)	7.2 (7.3)
$[Zn_4L'_2]$ (Grey)	18.7 (18.8)	34.2 (34.6)	1.4 (1.4)	8.1 (8.0)
$[Cd_4L'_2]$ (Reddish grey)	28.3 (28.5)	30.2 (30.4)	1.2 (1.2)	7.0 (7.1)
$[Hg_4L'_2]$ (Grey)	41.3 (41.6)	24.5 (24.9)	1.0 (1.0)	5.7 (5.9)

in both the ligands can be assigned to phenolic C–O vibration. In the metal chelates, this band appears at about 1480 cm^{-1} , showing the presence of bridging phenolic oxygen atom between two metal ions, supporting a polymeric structure². The positive shift of phenolic C–O vibration in the metal chelates indicates the existence of a oxo-bridged dimetallic structures³. Kauffmanet and Pandhye⁴ suggested the band at $770\text{--}780\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for phenolic oxygen bridging atom. Griffith⁵ observed a similar band at $710\text{--}790\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to oxo-bridged skelton in dimeric complexes. In the present case, a sharp band appearing at $725\text{--}730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ tentatively supports the polymeric oxo-bridged structure of the complexes. The sharp ligand bands at $1630\text{ (LH}_2\text{)}$ and $1620\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (L'H}_4\text{)}$ assigned to $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$, undergo hypsochromic shift by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the metal chelates, indicating bonding of one of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions⁶. In both the ligands, the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}\text{ COO}$ bands appear at ~ 1660 and $\sim 1430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. In the metal complexes these bands are observed at ~ 1560 , $\sim 1380\text{ (LH}_2\text{)}$ and ~ 1555 , $\sim 1375\text{ (L'H}_4\text{)}$ with a difference of about 180 cm^{-1} , indicative of monodentate coordination of the carboxy group⁷. In case of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, either a broad band or a double hump is observed at $3300\text{--}3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by sharp peak at $830\text{--}850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively, indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules⁸. The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are found to be anhydrous in nature. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligands to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of bands at $510\text{--}520\text{ (M-O)}$ and $410\text{--}430\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (M-N)}$ ⁹.

Magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are found to be 2.7, 2.5 and 1.4 B.M. respectively. Subnormal magnetic moments of the complexes support their polymeric structures with metal-metal interactions¹⁰.

The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit three $d\text{-}d$ bands at 8965 , 14495 and 23855 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, and a CT band at $\sim 35325\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Both the complexes are suggested to be octahedral¹¹ in nature based upon their ligand field parameters Dq , B , β_{35} , ν_2/ν_1

and σ values. In case of the Co^{II} complexes, four ligand field bands are observed at ~ 8642 , ~ 17350 , ~ 20480 and $\sim 34850\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the first three being attributed to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively, and the last one to a charge transfer transition. Hence, an octahedral symmetry¹² for the complexes may be suggested. The Cu^{II} complexes display a broad asymmetric ligand field band at $13370\text{--}14755$ (maxima at $\sim 14320\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a band at $\sim 30580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ and CT transition respectively. The broadening of this band can be ascribed to both Jahn-Teller distortion and contribution by mixed N, O donor atoms. The presence of a distorted octahedral stereochemistry¹³ around the Cu^{II} ions is indicated.

In the ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectrum of the ligand (LH_2), an unsymmetrical complex pattern is observed at $\delta 6.8\text{--}8.6$ indicating the presence of seven phenyl protons and a sharp peak $\delta 2.36$ corresponds to three methyl protons.

The esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes are recorded at X-band. In case of $[\text{Cu}_4\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]$ the esr peak is missing. It may be attributed to the presence of antiferromagnetic coupling between two copper ions achieved through the oxo-bridge. But in case of $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, a very weak peak is obtained. The g_{av} value is calculated to be 2.0623 using Kneubuhl's method¹⁴. This type of spectrum may result either due to the existence of dynamic or pseudorotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion or due to the extensive exchange coupling interactions between Cu–Cu ions in a dinuclear species¹⁵.

The above results supports a binuclear octahedral or distorted octahedral structure for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes and a tetrahedral dinuclear structure for the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with LH_2 , and a tetranuclear octahedral or distorted octahedral structure for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes and tetranuclear tetrahedral structure for the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with L'H_4 .

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. make. The azodyes were synthesised by the usual coupling reaction of diazonium chlorides obtained from *p*-toluidine

NOTE

and *m*-phenylenediamine separately with alkaline solution of 5-sulphosalicylic acid at 0°. The metal complexes were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of the metal(II) chlorides with the ligands dissolved in ethanol in 1 : 2 ratio. The pH of the reaction mixture was then raised to ~ 7 by adding concentrated ammonia dropwise with stirring. The resulting solid complexes were washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. M. K. Raval, Senior Lecturer, Rajendra College, Bolangir, for his valuable suggestion.

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